

Clinical Profile and Hepatic Dysfunction Pattern in Paediatric Dengue Infection: A Prospective Study from Bundelkhand Region of Central India

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ABSTRACT

Dengue is a common vector-borne disease, affecting all age groups resulting in significant morbidity. Hepatic dysfunction in pediatric dengue infection ranges from mild transaminitis to acute liver failure. This led us to study clinical profile and pattern of hepatic dysfunction in paediatric dengue infection of Bundelkhand region of India. This prospective study was conducted during June 2017 to October 2018. Study participants were enrolled and classified in three groups as per WHO 2009 classification. Clinical profile and laboratory parameters were recorded. Data were analyzed using STATA 15.0.

We enrolled 50 cases and classified them in dengue without Warning sign (WS) 21(42%), dengue with WS 24(48%) and severe dengue 5(10%). Commonest presenting symptom and sign were fever (100%) and hepatomegaly (42%) respectively. Pain abdomen, mucosal bleeding and hepatomegaly were significantly more in dengue with WS (p value <0.001, 0.006 and <0.001 respectively). Gastrointestinal bleeding, neurological symptoms and shock were significantly present in severe dengue (p value <0.001 for all). Hemoglobin, hematocrit, serum protein were significantly decreased in severe dengue (p value- 0.012, 0.007 and 0.023 respectively). However, Total leucocyte count, Prothombin Time and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time were significantly elevated (p value 0.008, 0.012 and 0.0223 respectively). Mean serum transaminases were elevated in all groups and were comparable. Elevated serum transaminases were recorded in all patients with dengue infection; however these laboratory findings do not differentiate between severe and non-severe dengue infection.

KEY WORDS: dengue, hepatic dysfunction, hepatomegaly

INTRODUCTION:

Dengue is an important vector-borne arboviral infection, which has emerged as a major public health problem worldwide and mostly endemic in tropical and subtropical countries including India^[1].

In India, dengue is endemic to almost all states and a major cause of hospitalization in rainy and post-rainy season. Despite of all preventive measures, numbers of dengue cases have increased from 1,01,192 in 2018 to 1,36,422 till November 2019 with relative decline in number of deaths from 172 to 132

respectively^[2]. Major demographic changes such as uncontrolled population, unplanned urbanization, substandard housing and poor water drainage has facilitated vector proliferation.

Dengue is caused by Dengue virus (DEN), which is single, stranded RNA virus belonging to Flaviviridae. There are five serotypes namely DEN-1, DEN-2, DEN-3, DEN-4 and DEN-5 have been isolated till now. Transmission is mostly by *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes and *Aedes albopictus* is secondary vector which has characteristics of being highly adaptive and can survive in cooler climates too. All serotypes/ genotypes are now circulating globally and maintaining hyperendemicity. DEN-2 viral infection has propensity to cause severe signs and symptoms. DEN-2 and DEN-3 have been mostly linked with dengue hemorrhagic fever. Infection by one serotype provides lifelong immunity to that serotype, but gives transient and partial protection to other serotypes.

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Sequential infection with different serotypes increases risk of severe dengue.

As Per WHO 2009 classification, dengue fever has been classified as: (i) dengue without warning signs(WS), (ii) dengue with WS and (iii) severe dengue. Dengue infection is frequently confounded with other febrile illnesses (OFI), presenting with non-specific clinical symptoms analogous to OFI. During the early course of dengue infection, presence of nonspecific febrile illness makes precise diagnosis strikingly difficult, resulting in inefficient treatment and possible increases in morbidity and mortality. Severe dengue, if not appropriately managed, may lead to rapid death, particularly in children. In addition, the lack of necessary laboratory facilities, particularly in remote/rural areas may cause difficulty in discriminating dengue infection from OFI.

Diagnosis of dengue by virus isolation has been the traditional and definitive diagnostic method for detecting DENV infection; however it is not practical as testing result may take days to weeks. So, gradually it was replaced by Real time- polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) and now more recently, by Non Structural Protein1 Antigen (NS1Ag) captured enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) and Immunoglobulin M antibody (IgM Ab) ELISAs for more rapid diagnosis. These are principal diagnostic modalities in endemic countries because of their cost-effectiveness and higher sensitivity and specificity. NS1 Ag has a sensitivity of around 80% and specificity of 99- 100%^[3].

Studies have been done on various aspects of dengue infection across the world and India. However, there is paucity of data regarding paediatric dengue infection from Bundelkhand region of central India. Hence, this research was conducted to study the clinico-epidemiological aspects and profile of hepatic dysfunction in children with dengue infection from this region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

After getting approval from Institutional Ethical Committee, this hospital based prospective observational study was conducted during June 2017 to October 2018 in the Department of Pediatrics of Maharani Laxmi Bai Medical College, a tertiary care teaching institute in Jhansi, Uttar Pradesh, India.

All laboratory confirmed Dengue fever (either IgM or NS1Antigen or both positive) patients between ages 1 month to 18 years, getting admitted in this department were enrolled as study participants

after getting an informed written consent. We excluded patients aged >18 years, patients with pre-existing liver disease, patients with bleeding disorders and patients not willing to be a part of this study.

Pre-designed, pretested proforma was used by primary investigator to collect data, which includes patient's particulars: name, age, sex and date of hospitalization; clinical symptoms at presentation like fever, headache, bodyache, joint pain, rashes, pain abdomen, vomiting, bleeding manifestation (epistaxis, gum bleeding and malena) abnormal movements or altered sensorium; detailed physical signs like circulatory status (presence or absence of shock), pallor, icterus, petechiae, organomegaly (hepatomegaly and/or splenomegaly), ascites, pleural effusion and laboratory parameters at admission like NS1Ag, IgM Dengue, hemoglobin (Hb), hematocrit (HCT), total leukocyte count (TLC), platelet count (PC), serum bilirubin (S. bil.), S. alanine transferase (ALT), S. aspartate transaminase (AST), S. alkaline phosphatase (ALP), prothombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT), S. protein and S. albumin. Shock was defined as, if the pulse pressure (i.e. the difference between the systolic and diastolic pressures) was ≤ 20 mm Hg in children or he/she had signs of poor capillary perfusion (cold extremities, delayed capillary refill, or rapid pulse rate)^[3].

Study participants were categorized as dengue without WS, dengue with WS and severe dengue as per WHO 2009 Classification. Warning signs include abdominal pain or tenderness, persistent vomiting, clinical fluid accumulation, mucosal bleed, lethargy or restlessness, liver enlargement >2 cm and laboratory parameter i.e. increase in HCT concurrent with rapid decrease in platelet count. Severe dengue includes (a) severe plasma leakage leading to shock or fluid accumulation with respiratory distress (b) severe bleeding as evaluated by clinician and (c) severe organ involvement of liver (AST or ALT ≥ 1000), neurological system (impaired consciousness) and heart or other organs.

Data was entered in Microsoft excel sheet 2007 and analyzed using software STATA 15.0 (StataCorp). Pearson chi-squared test (χ^2) was applied for categorical data to look for any significance. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Kruskal Wallis tests were used for comparing different explanatory variables among three categories of outcome variable as per their distribution. Post-hoc analysis was done using Bonferroni test for normally distributed variables while rank-sum test with adjusted level of significance was used for the variables which did not

follow the normal distribution. p-value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant. Study was discontinued when predefined study period was over.

RESULTS:

Total 85 patients of acute febrile illness were assessed for eligibility, 35 patients were excluded with different reasons [Figure:1] and 50 study participants were included and classified into dengue without WS in 21 (42%), dengue with WS in 24 (48.0%) and severe dengue in 5 (10%). Mean age of enrolled participants were comparable in all three groups and majority of them 22 (44%) were in the age group of 5-10 years. 56% of the cases were boys.

All study participants had fever as presenting complaint. Other common symptoms were abdominal pain 34 (68%), headache 24 (48%), vomiting 20 (40%) and rashes 15 (30%) [Table-1]. Bodyache was significantly more in dengue without WS (p value-0.022). However, pain abdomen and skin/mucosal bleeding were significantly more in dengue with WS (p value- <0.001 and 0.006 respectively). Gastrointestinal bleeding, altered sensorium and abnormal movements were significantly more in severe dengue (p value- <0.001, <0.001 and <0.001 respectively). Most common physical sign was hepatomegaly in 21 (42%). Shock was significantly more in severe dengue group (p value- <0.001) while icterus and hepatomegaly were significantly more in dengue with WS (p value- <0.049 and <0.001 respectively). Remaining clinical parameters were comparable in all three groups [Table: 1].

In lab parameters, mean Hb and mean HCT in dengue without WS was comparable with dengue with WS and severe dengue; however, these parameters were significantly lower in severe dengue than dengue with WS (p value- 0.013 and 0.006 respectively). Mean TLC in dengue without WS group and dengue with WS group was comparable (p value-1.000); however, it was significantly elevated in severe dengue group, as compared to dengue without WS and dengue with WS group (p value- 0.010 and 0.008 respectively). S. proteins were significantly higher in dengue with WS group (p value- 0.023) [Table: 2]. PT and aPTT were significantly elevated in severe dengue (p value- 0.012 and 0.022 respectively). Remaining lab parameters like Mean S. AST, S. ALT, mean PC, S. bilirubin and S. ALP were comparable in all three groups.

DISCUSSION:

In this study, we analyzed 50 study participants; out of which 45 (90%) were categorized

as nonsevere dengue which included both dengue fever with and without warning signs and 5 (10%) were severe dengue, similar to study by Tamibmaniam et al who noted lower prevalence of severe dengue (9%)^[4]. Fewer number of severe dengue cases can be attributed to access to health facility, early detection of disease progression and ensuring close observation.

In the present study, boys and girls were almost equally affected with 56% and 44% of total cases respectively. It was in accordance with previously reported data by Rose et al^[5]. Children in age group of 5-10 years constituted almost half of dengue cases (44%) which is in accordance to study by Kulkarni et al, where 45.8% cases were in 6-12 yrs of age group^[6].

Commonest presenting symptom was fever (100%) followed by headache (46%) and rashes (30%). Bodyache (23.81%) was exclusively and significantly present in dengue without WS (p value-0.022) similar to study by Rathore et al where myalgia was reported in 27.33% cases^[7]. However, a higher incidence of body ache (79.20%) has been reported by Gupta et al have in a study of 48 dengue patients^[8].

Warning sign like abdominal pain was present in 46% of cases which was comparable to earlier studies having an incidence of 30 to 55%. Abdominal pain was significantly present in dengue with WS (79.16%) and severe dengue (80%) (p value- <0.001), which was similar with the findings of Roy et al for severe dengue (79.4%) but, with a lower incidence in dengue with WS group (21.9%). Vomiting was present in 20 (40%) cases, similar to incidence reported by Rathore et al^[7].

Mucosal bleed (epistaxis/gum bleeding) was significantly more in dengue with WS group (p value-0.006). However, severe (GI) bleeding was significant finding in severe dengue group (p value- <0.001) similar to study by Mishra et al^[9]. Neurological manifestations like abnormal movements 3 (60%) and altered sensorium 4 (80%) was seen only in severe dengue group (p value <0.001 and <0.001 respectively). Petechiae were present in 26% of all cases similar to 22.1% in study by Mishra et al^[9].

Hepatomegaly (42%) was commonest physical sign noted in our study, which is in accordance with the findings reported by Mishra et al. Hepatomegaly in children with dengue infection has been reported in 43-100% of cases in similar studies^[10]. Incidence of hepatomegaly was higher in severe dengue as compared to dengue with WS group, similar to studies by Wahid et al and Wichman et al

Table 1: Clinico-demographic profile of study participants.

Variables	Dengue without WS	Dengue with WS	Severe Dengue	p-value
	Group I [§] n=21 (%)	Group II [§] n= 24 (%)	Group III [§] n=5 (%)	
Baseline characteristics				
Male	12 (57.14%)	13 (57.17%)	3 (60%)	0.963
Age (Years)*	9.55 ±4.68	9.81 ±3.84	8.72 ±4.80	0.873
Dengue serology				0.123
NS1 Antigen	13 (61.90%)	9 (37.50%)	0 (0%)	
IgM Dengue	5 (23.81%)	8 (33.33%)	3 (60%)	
NS1 & IgM	3 (14.29%)	7 (29.17%)	2 (40%)	
Clinical Symptoms				
Fever	21 (100%)	24 (100%)	5 (100%)	NA
Headache	9 (42.86%)	13 (54.17%)	1(20%)	0.352
Rashes	7 (33.33%)	7 (29.17%)	1(20%)	0.836
Pain abdomen	0 (0%)	19 (79.17%)	4 (80%)	<0.001
Vomiting	10 (47.62%)	9 (37.50%)	1 (20%)	0.496
Joint pain	2 (9.52%)	0%(0)	0%(0)	0.237
Bodyache	5 (23.81%)	0%(0)	0%(0)	0.022
Mucosal Bleed	0 (0%)	8 (33.33%)	0 (0%)	0.006
Gastrointestinal bleeding	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (60%)	<0.001
Altered sensorium	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (80%)	<0.001
Abnormal movement	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (60%)	<0.001
Physical signs				
Shock	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (100.0%)	<0.001
Pallor	8 (38.10%)	5 (20.83%)	3 (60%)	0.171
Icterus	1 (4.76%)	7 (29.17%)	0 (0%)	0.049
petechiae	3 (14.29%)	7 (29.17%)	3 (60%)	0.099
Hepatomegaly	0 (0%)	12 (50%)	3 (60%)	<0.001
Ascites	0 (0%)	4 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0.095
Spleen	2 (9.52%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0.237
Pleural effusion	0 (0%)	2 (8.33%)	0 (0%)	0.324

[§]n – number of participants, *Age expressed as mean±SD.

who reported higher incidence of hepatomegaly in DHF and DSS respectively as compared to non-severe dengue fever^[11,12]. However, study by Roy et al reported higher incidences in dengue with WS (84.4%) and severe dengue (93.1%)^[13]. Icterus was observed significantly more in dengue with WS (29.1%) (p value- 0.049).

All cases in severe dengue (100%) presented with shock (p <0.001), similar to study by Roy et al-(13). Mean Hb and HCT were comparable between dengue without WS vs dengue with WS and dengue without WS vs. severe dengue; however, it was significantly low in severe dengue as compared to dengue with WS (p value- 0.013 and 0.006 respectively). Apparent elevation in mean Hb and

HCT in dengue with WS group can be explained with hemoconcentration because of fluid leak; however fall in severe dengue can be attributed to severe bleeding.

Elevated hepatic enzymes have been reported in dengue patients by various researchers, ranging from 36.4% to 96% in different pediatric and adult studies. In our study, we observed that AST was higher than ALT, similar to previous reported studies^[9,13]. Elevated AST levels can be attributed to dengue infection induced damage to non-hepatic tissue. Prolonged PT and aPTT in severe dengue was in accordance with Roy et al where they reported prolonged INR in place of PT; however Jagdishkumar et al reported only significantly pronged INR in

Table 2: Laboratory parameters of study participants

Lab parameters	Dengue without WS [Group I]*	Dengue with WS [Group II]*	Severe Dengue [Group III]*	p-value	[§] Post hoc pair wise comparison		
					Group I vs Group II	Group I vs Group III	Group II vs Group III
Hb (gm/dl)	9.76±2.14	10.73±1.81	7.88±1.46	0.012	0.307	0.169	0.013
TLC(cells/mm ³)	5678.57±5215.95	5561.25±3779.57	12700.0±5134.69	0.008	1.000	0.010	0.008
PCV (%)	29.42±7.75	32.27±6.50	21.14±3.98	0.007	0.520	0.060	0.006
PC(lac cells/mm ³)	0.72±0.30	0.59±0.30	0.62±0.18	0.324			
S. bil. (mg/dl)	0.74±0.36	1.19±0.91	1.52±1.41	0.069			
S. bil (direct)	0.46±0.22	0.75±0.61	0.92±0.86	0.085			
AST (IU/ml)	111.98±112.16	153.37±128.44	202.60±110.78	0.258			
ALT(IU/ml)	94.90±101.59	94.70±79.85	116.94±73.24	0.871			
S. ALP (IU/ml)	313.52±113.08	376.21±128.43	363.68±177.20	0.257			
PT (sec)	13.77±2.27	16.03±6.60	23.90±14.97	0.012	0.756	0.009	0.054
APTT (sec)	26.11±6.06	33.65±14.80	41.52±17.24	0.022	0.131	0.043	0.585
S.protein (gm/dl)	6.28±0.93	6.49±1.13	5.01±1.17	0.023	1.000	0.060	0.019
S. albumin(gm/dl)	3.82±0.74	3.98±0.96	2.97±0.87	0.069			

*Data expressed as mean±SD, [§]Post hoc pair wise comparison, if p value was <0.05

children with dengue shock syndrome^[14]. Mechanisms of hepatic injury in dengue infection could be either direct effects of the virus or host immune response, circulatory compromise, hypoxia, metabolic acidosis or localized vascular leakage inside liver, hepatotoxic drugs and tissue tropism of particular viral serotypes or genotypes.

We observed significant hypoproteinemia in severe dengue group as compared to non-severe dengue (p value-0.023). Observations of serum albumin was similar to findings reported by Jagdishkumar et al and findings of hypoproteinemia was similar to study by Prasad et al except for S. albumin which was significantly decreased in severe dengue group^[15].

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

Only laboratory confirmed dengue cases were included. Sample size was small. Findings of deranged liver function was not adjusted for the presence of other co-infections in this region like malaria, enteric fever and chikungunya, having propensity to cause hepatitis.

CONCLUSION:

We conclude that, spectrum of hepatic involvement in dengue infection ranges from elevation of liver enzyme to clinical jaundice to acute liver failure. Hepatomegaly is a most important physical sign. Child presenting with fever, hepatomegaly and altered liver function, possibility of

Figure 1: Flow chart of study participants included in this study.

dengue infection should be strongly kept in endemic zones. Elevated liver enzymes were present in non-severe dengue group as well, reflecting hepatic injury in all stages of the disease. A further study from this region with large sample size would be helpful in answering pattern of liver dysfunction with severity of illness, its relation with other common co-infections and its effect on disease outcome.

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